

automatically disintegrated and mixed with the soil within a week. No manual mixing was necessary and there was no sign of injury to the rice crop.

The legume increased rice germination by 21% under the crust and affected the lateritic upland situation. Twenty-day-old sesbania bearing 7 to 17 nodules/plant contributed 4.3-6.3 t green manure/ha.

Grain yield increased significantly (see table). The yield with sesbania alone equaled yield with 40 kg N/ha. □

Effects of nitrogen and sesbania on number of nodules, green matter from sesbania, plant population, and rice yield. Orissa, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Sesbania nodules/plant ^a (no.)	Sesbania green matter incorporated (t/ha) ^a	Rice plants/m ²		Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Without sesbania	With sesbania	Without sesbania	With sesbania
0	6.8	4.3	274	326	1.1	1.4
20	12.8	4.8	277	241	1.2	1.5
30	13.2	5.6	218	345	1.3	1.5
40	15.6	5.8	252	313	1.5	1.8
50	17.0	6.3	280	359	1.6	2.1
Mean	13.10	5.4	260	316	1.3	1.6
CD (0.05)						0.2

^aTreatments had received 50% N at time of data collection.

Split application of slow-release urea

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We studied the comparative efficiency and time of application of slow-release urea materials such as neem cake-coated urea (NCCU, 20% neem cake powder), coal tar-coated urea (CTCU, 1% coal tar), urea supergranule (USG, 1-g size), and prilled urea (PU) in 2 soil types.

ADT36 (110 d, Jun-Sep 1984) and IR20 (135 d, Sep 1984-Feb 1985) were tested in the clayey loam soils of Aduthurai (silty clay to clay, Vertisol, clay 40% low in N) where 2 rice crops are usually grown. IR20 (medium duration, Jul-Dec 1984) was tested in the sandy loam soils of Pattukottai (sandy loam, Alfisol, clay 12.0% low in N). The recommended NPK of 75.0-

Effect of split application of slow-release urea on yield. India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	Clay soil		Sandy loam soil
	Crop 1	Crop 2	
<i>Source</i>			
NCCU	4.6	4.6	4.6
CTCU	4.8	4.7	4.7
USG	5.0	4.7	5.0
PU	4.4	4.5	4.7
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2
<i>Time of application</i>			
Single basal (slow-release urea)	4.5	4.6	4.5
Single basal (50% slow-release + 50% PU)	4.5	4.5	4.5
Split application ^a (slow-release urea)	5.0	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal PU + topdressed slow-release urea)	4.9	4.7	4.9
Split application ^a (basal slow-release + topdressed PU)	4.6	4.8	4.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	ns	0.2

^aSplit application = 50% N before planting, 50% N at maximum tillering.

37.5-37.5 kg/ha for the 110-d variety and 100-50-50 kg/ha for the 135-d variety were applied.

USG gave significantly higher yields than PU in both soil types (see table).

Yields with NCCU and CTCU only equaled that with PU. Split application of slow-release urea gave higher yields than single basal in both soils. □

Effect of soil moisture regime and straw incorporation on root growth and yield of rice

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We conducted a lysimeter experiment with rice variety PR106 on a calcareous sandy loam soil (Typic

Ustochrept). Air-dried soil was passed through a 2-mm sieve and used to fill iron barrels 1 m high with 50-cm internal diameter. The treatments, replicated 3 times, were combinations of 3 levels of straw incorporation (no straw, 1% straw, and 2% straw) and 3 soil moisture regimes (field capacity, saturation, and submergence). Straw was chopped into 2- to 4-cm pieces and mixed into the top 15 cm of soil.

The soil moisture treatments were imposed after 3 wk of continuous submergence following transplanting. To attain field capacity, 4-6 cm water was applied 24 h after infiltration of water previously applied. Saturation was 0-1.5 cm ponded water; submergence was 4-6 cm ponded water. Fertilizer was applied at 150 kg N and 13 kg P/ha.

Depth of roots was determined at

maturity by excavating and washing the soil in the 0-5, 5-10, and 10-25 cm layers. Roots were rewashed and dried at 60°C. Rooting density was expressed as weight of dry roots per unit volume of soil. Root weight index was total root weight per cm² soil surface in the entire (0-25 cm) root zone.

Soil moisture regime significantly affected root distribution (see table). Root weight index increased with water supply. Incorporation of straw significantly decreased the root weight index and rooting density in all three layers. However, in the surface (0-5 cm) layer, the fraction of total roots increased from 34% under no straw to 38% when 2% straw was incorporated, showing that higher soil reduction increased the fraction of the total roots in the surface layer.

Incorporation of straw also

Effect of soil moisture regime and straw incorporation on root growth and yield of rice. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Rooting density ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$) at indicated depth			Root weight index (mg/cm^2)	Yield (g/pot)
	0-5 cm deep	5-10 cm deep	10-25 cm deep		
<i>Moisture regime</i>					
Field capacity	482	415	157	7.3	107
Saturation	661	502	287	10.1	206
Submergence	995	567	377	13.5	234
<i>Straw treatment</i>					
No straw	891	728	329	13.0	235
1% straw	702	479	287	10.2	169
2% straw	538	277	203	7.1	143
CD (0.05)					
Moisture regime or straw	174	117	172	3.0	19

decreased the rice grain yield significantly. The grain yield was linearly related to the root weight index ($R^2 = 0.93$). The reduction in root growth and grain yield was probably due to the accumulation of toxic substances in the root zone, under highly reduced conditions

provided by the decomposition of added straw. This also appears to be the likely reason for significantly higher grain yield under submergence than under saturation, since the toxic substances will be better leached under continued submergence than under saturation. □

Influence of moisture regime on IR50

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An experiment was conducted on water needs of IR50 during summer and kharif 1985. Four irrigation treatments were evaluated: continuous submergence (5 cm), 5-cm depth to saturation, saturation up to and after heading and 5-cm water during heading (panicle initiation to flowering), and saturation at 25% depletion of available soil moisture (DASM). The experiment was in a randomized block design with eight replications.

IR50 yield and water use efficiency.

Treatment	1985 dry season (summer)			1985 wet season (kharif)		
	Total water applied (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency	Total water applied (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency
Continuous submergence (5 cm)	1850	6.2	3.34	1399	6.4	4.55
Saturation to 5 cm	986	6.6	6.67	1141	6.6	5.75
Saturation up to and after heading and 5 cm during heading	1205	6.4	5.29	1055	6.2	5.88
Saturation at 25% DASM	620	5.7	9.18	685	5.5	8.06
CD at 5%		0.5			1.0	

During the dry season, irrigation to saturation to 5-cm depth consumed 47% of the water required by continuous submergence (see table). This trend continued in the wet season, with a saving of 18% of the irrigation

water. Irrigation to saturation at 25% DASM consumed the least irrigation water (620 mm in summer and 685 mm in wet season) and yield was reduced by only 11% (on the average) for a higher water use efficiency. □

P and K requirements of upland rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh

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We studied the effect of P and K on yield and yield components of rainfed upland rice variety IET7613 (85 d maturity) during 1985 at Faizabad. Soil was sandy loam with 22.5% field capacity and 4.6% wilting point of the 0-15 cm soil profile. Bulk density was

1.42 g/cm³. Total rainfall during the crop season was 920 mm with monthly distributions of 92 mm (Jun), 374 mm (Jul), 140 mm (Aug), 197 mm (Sep), and 117 mm (Oct). The rice crop faced 3 dry spells: 6 d during the first 14 d of Jul, 7 d during mid-Aug, and 11 d